

Mechanical Engineering in Ancient Egypt, Part 106: Archaeological Projects

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Abstract:

This is the 106 paper in a series of research papers exploring the history of mechanical engineering during the Ancient Egyptian era. The paper presents a number of archaeological projects for archaeological graduates and experts in Egypt and world wise. The situation of the artifacts recommended for the projects is really miserable and requires ancient scientific activities to save them. These projects will enhance the knowledge of the whole world with the ancient Egyptian civilization sustained for thousands of years. Steps and typical examples are presented to clarify the idea of each project.

Keywords — Mechanical engineering history, Ancient Egypt, archaeological projects, application steps and examples.

I. INTRODUCTION

For more than 40 years working as a staff member in the Department of Mechanical Engineering and Design at Cairo University of Egypt I have supervised 10's of projects for undergraduate and postgraduate students. Through my research in the subject of Mechanical Engineering in ancient Egypt and the publication of more than 100 research papers I have gained experience helping me to assign some archaeological projects required to enhance the existence of artefacts inside Egypt requiring extensive care through restoration or replication. This is one of two many things required by all Egyptologists to enhance the feeling of the rights of the ancient Egyptian civilization.

Farid (2001) investigated the digital reconstruction of the ancient Egyptian tombs from pyramids time to the tombs of Thebes. He addressed the problems facing photographing and reconstruction of those tombs and the techniques for removing image distortions, recovering 3D shape and correcting the lighting imbalances. He presented a complete reconstruction of Sennedjem's tomb [1]. Aronin (2012) discussed the 3D computer reconstruction by the Giza Project at Harvard of the

tomb of Queen Meresankh III, grandmother of King Khufu and wife of his son Khafre. The work allowed scholars to view the tomb as it appeared when constructed 4500 years ago [2]. Brand and Revez (2012) presented a field work report for the joint mission organized in 2011 by the University of Quebec a Montreal and University of Memphis. The purpose of the mission was to study the 134 columns inside the Hypostyle Hall of the Amen Re Temple at Karnak and make facsimile copies of the columns [3].

Wong (2013) presented a bibliography for the project of conservation and management of the tomb of Pharaoh Tutankhamen as a joint project between the Getty Conservation Institute (at Los Angeles) and the Ministry of State of the Antiquities (of Egypt). He organized the bibliography by subject according to the three phases of the project. Some of the subjects were: Background and history, condition, original materials and technology, sarcophagus, coffin and mummy, conservation treatment, environmental conditions, site and visitor management [4]. Ahmed (2014) investigated the furniture industry in ancient Egypt through scenes in the tombs and actual models and units displayed in various museums. He concentrated on the chairs and stools from different dynastic eras [5]. Hassaan (2016) in a series of research papers on mechanical engineering in

ancient Egypt investigated some of the important industries practiced in the ancient Egyptian society including: Furniture industry [6], jewellery industry [7] – [13], pottery industry [14]-[17], stone vessels industry [18], [19], faience industry [20], glass industry [21], ladies headdress industry [22], [23], textile industry [24], women clothing industry [25]-[27] and models industry [28].

Hassaan (2017) investigated more industries practiced in ancient Egypt including the alabaster products industry [29], [30], basketry industry [31], foot wearing industry [32] and semiprecious stones applications [33]. Di Paola, Milazzo and Spatafora (2017) described the workflow of a 3D acquisition and graphical modelling to assist the conservation of the legs of the throne of Zens Enthroned integrated with the missing parts. They concluded that the application of the 3D digital technologies was a useful tool for improving the conservation of a work of the art [34]. Di Paolo and Inzerillo (2018) presented a pipeline developed to acquire a shape with particular features under geometric and radiometric aspects. They used the technique to build 3D model for the black stone of Palermo. For the texture reconstruction they used a last generation smart phone [35].

Connor (2018) presented images for incomplete sculptures from Paris, Philadelphia, London, Cairo, Chicago, Karnak, Elephantine, Vienna, Detroit and Lucerne [36]. Devillers (2018) presented a general colored view of the tomb of Pahery from the 18th Dynasty. She presented a description for the tomb and the other tombs connected to Bahery's tomb with comparison between the scenes encountered. Her work can be considered as a good record for the scenes in the studied tombs [37]. Hassaan (2018) investigated the inscription of temples of the ancient Egyptians during a time period from the 12th Dynasty to the 30th Dynasty [38]. Wong and Quintero (2019) discussed the 3D digital revolution, the role of replicas in cultural heritage, 3D digital documentation using laser scanning and photogrammetry. They compared the two tombs of Tutankhamen: the original and the replica tombs [39].

Hassaan (2019) investigated the boats industry in ancient Egypt during a period from the Predynastic

Period to the Middle Kingdom [40], boats industry during the New Kingdom and Late Period [41], pigment industry during the Old and Middle Kingdoms [42], pigment industry during the New Kingdom [43], diadem industry [44] and sceptres industry [45]. Bayoumy and Elsokaily (2020) studied the use of three gemstones in ancient Egypt: lapis lazuli, turquoise and carnelian, their uses, sources, religious significance and color symbolism [46]. Hassaan (2020) investigated the tombs inscription during the Old Kingdom [47], during the 11th and 12th Dynasties [48], during the 18th Dynasty [49] and during the 19th and 20th Dynasties [50]. Florek et. al. (2021) examined a wooden boat model in the Australian Museum to assess its identity and age. They presented photo images for the complete boat and X-ray images for specific sections of it. They concluded that the model was attributed to a period between Late Old Kingdom and Early Middle Kingdom [51].

Hassaan (2021) investigated the use of kinematic joints in ancient Egypt during the 6th to 19th Dynasties [52], the temples columns industry during a time span from the 4th Dynasty to the Late Period [53] and the tomb pillars industry during a time span from the 4th to the 20th Dynasties [54]. Hassaan (2022) investigated the bowls industry during a time span from Predynastic to the 18th Dynasty Periods. He presented examples for bowls manufactured using various materials, designs and uses [55].

II. FIRST PROJECT: EXHIBITIONS FOR THE MECHANICAL INDUSTRIES IN ANCIENT EGYPT

Exhibition idea:

- 1- The idea of the exhibition is based on collecting some of the documented products produced by the ancient Egyptians and presenting them in the form of industries such as: the furniture industry - the jewelry industry - the alabaster products industry ... and so on.
- 2- Each industry is presented in the form of power point slides, so that each industry is in a separate file.

- 3- Allocating a showroom equipped with screens measuring 2 meters x 2 meters and operating with a flash.
- 4- The exhibition areas can be in museums, institutes, universities, culture centers or squares.
- 5- One screen is allocated for each industry.
- 6- For exhibitions in a hall, 25-30 screens is needed.
- 7- Each hall has a technical director and one youth beside each screen to answer visitors' inquiries.

Here are samples of the photos of the products of some industries practiced through the ancient Egyptian civilization:

- From the jewelry industry: Fig.1 shows a necklace for Princess Sathathor from the 12th Dynasty [8].

Fig.1 Necklace from the 12th Dynasty [8].

- From the pottery industry: Fig.2 shows a pottery jar for Artisan Sennedjem from the 19th Dynasty [15].
- From the stoneware industry: Fig.3 shows a gneiss bowl from the 4th Dynasty [18].
- From the glass industry: Fig.4 shows a glass jug from the 18th Dynasty [21].
- From the women headdress industry: Fig.5 shows a woman headdress from the 18th Dynasty [23].
- From the basketry industry: Fig.6 shows a basket from the 18th Dynasty [31].

- From the diadem industry: Fig.7 shows a diadem from the 12th Dynasty [44].

Fig.2 Pottery jar from the 19th Dynasty [15].

Fig.3 Gneiss bowl from the 4th Dynasty [18].

Fig.4 Glass jug from the 18th Dynasty [21].

Fig.5 Lady headdress from the 18th Dynasty [23].

Fig.6 Basket from the 18th Dynasty [31].

Fig.7 Diadem from the 12th Dynasty [44].

III. SECOND PROJECT: MAKING QUALITATIVE REPLICAS FOR SPECIFIC PRODUCTS

The ancient Egyptians were pioneers in producing items having extremely high quality which deserve reproducing some of them (if possible) and presenting them to the present humanity as examples of the production of the ancient Egyptian civilization. The idea of the project is based on:

- 1- Choosing specific pioneering products that is possible to be replicated.
- 2- For example: the manufacture of jewelry - furniture - alabaster products - fine pottery – faience - stoneware - glass products - women's headdress - women's clothing - the inlay of products with semi-precious stones.
- 3- Permanent or mobile exhibitions for those products can be held in museums, archaeological sites, cultural places, archaeological conference locations, Egyptian cultural consulates abroad, and in permanent exhibitions in official exhibition lands.
- 4- An advertisement for the project will be carried out in various audio, visual and written media at the expense of the Ministry of Youth to encourage young people to build their business and expand those projects.
- 5- Senior officials and ambassadors of foreign countries are invited to inaugurate these projects to encourage the presentation of these exhibitions in their countries.
- 6- For example, the alabaster workshops in Qurna, Luxor, produce alabaster units through their own experience and sure they

can produce any assigned products by the directories of this project.

- 7- In addition, for a project such as the manufacture of jewelry and other industries, it is possible to contract with Khan Al-Khalili stores to distribute with sufficient advertising and reasonable prices that can compete with what enters Egypt from some foreign countries.
- 8- It is possible to enter the field of electronic sales through the Internet and to provide a work team of young people for this task, along with providing a delivery service to homes and sales stores (as an alternative, it is possible to contract with big online shopping companies such as Amazon and Jumia).

Examples of good products of the ancient Egyptians that may be covered by this project are presented in:

- Figures 1, 2, 4 and 6.
- Fig.7: Jewelry box from the 18th Dynasty [6].

Fig.7 Jewelry box from the 18th Dynasty [6].

- Fig.8: Lotus-flower-shaped faience cup from the 19th Dynasty [20].

Fig.8 Lotus-flower-shaped faience cup from the 19th Dynasty [20].

- Fig.9: Boat model from the tomb of Pharaoh Amenhotep II of the 18th Dynasty [28].

Fig.9 Boat model from the 18th Dynasty [28].

- Fig.10: Robe of the mother of Nakhtamun, Sculptor of Pharaoh Ramses II from the 19th Dynasty [27]. The robe is covering the whole body.

Fig.10 Robe from the 19th Dynasty [27].

IV. THIRD PROJECT: REPLICAS OF ANCIENT EGYPTIAN TOMBS

The ancient Egyptian tombs were an underground structures designed and carved in rock for the burial of the ancient Egyptians. They decorated the walls of the tombs of their Kings and Nobles by colored scenes reflecting the daily life in their society in a way preserving their civilization through professional documentation.

The idea of the project is based on:

- 1- Producing replicas for some of the tombs of the ancient Egyptians, such as: Tombs of the Kings Exhibition – Tombs of the Queens Exhibition - Tombs of the Nobles Exhibition.
- 2- The replicas may be structured underground simulating the actual tombs or on-surface.
- 3- Kings-tombs replicas will be for those whose drawings are preserved without vandalism. For example, tombs of: Thutmose III - Tutankhamen - Ramses I - Seti I - Ramses III - Ramses IX.
- 4- The colored drawings of the tombs will be digitally printed with high resolution on square papers with variable surface area depending on the actual tomb.
- 5- Every picture is given a number written on one of the corners of the figure.
- 6- These tomb-photos can be duplicated for sale, where copies of all the photos can be prepared and kept in stock.
- 7- Extra-large sizes can be prepared on order to suit the decoration of flats, palaces or hotels walls.
- 8- Steps 2 to 7 can be repeated for the tombs of queens, such as the tombs of: Merisankh III of the 4th Dynasty - Nefertari of the 19th Dynasty - and Titi of the 20th Dynasty.
- 9- Steps 2 to 7 can be repeated for tombs of the nobles, such as the tombs of: Nibamun - Mina - Rekhmire - Sennefer - Nakht - Userhat - Roy - Amenemhat and others.
- 10- To clarify the idea, we present a scene from the tomb of the noble Sennefer, Mayor of Thebes, during the reign of Pharaoh Amenhotep II of the 18th Dynasty and a relief from the tomb of Pharaoh Ramses III from the 20th Dynasty.

Fig.12 Carved relief for Pharaoh Ramses III from the 20th Dynasty [57].

V. FOURTH PROJECT: RESTORATION OF ANCIENT EGYPTIAN TOMBS

- 1- An important national project aimed at restoring the tombs of the nobles and other ancient tombs that were vandalized by tomb robbers.
- 2- The project is national because the tombs of the ancient Egyptians are a tourist attraction that could generate millions of dollars annually for the state.
- 3- Since almost most of the tombs of the nobles in Luxor have been affected by criminal vandalism, such a project will find great support from the state and UNESCO.

- 4- Each team consists of some qualified graduates and staff of the faculties of archaeology in local and international institutes
- 5- Each team takes over a cemetery.
- 6- The team is restoring the tomb drawings using the same scenes and the same colors used by the ancient Egyptians, not the modern ones.
- 7- The restoration of each tomb is suitable for being an independent project that the team can present to the Academy of Scientific Research for funding or the Ministry of Tourism or the Ministry of Antiquities.
- 8- These projects are not easy, and their budgets will be large. On the other hand, it is necessary to agree with high officials to provide adequate and advanced protection schemes for those tombs so that they are not stolen again.
- 9- Examples of the destruction that befell some of the tombs of the nobles are presented in Figs.13-17.

- Fig.13: Scene from the tomb of Scribe Nebamun from the 18th Dynasty [58].

Fig.13 Scene in Nebamun's tomb from the 18th Dynasty [58].

- Fig.14: Sad view from the tomb of Mayer Sennefer from the 18th Dynasty [59].
- Fig.15: Scene from the tomb of Vizier Rekhmire from the 18th Dynasty [60].

- Fig.16: Scene from the tomb of Scribe Menna from the 18th Dynasty [61].
- Fig.17: Scene from the tomb of Scribe Nakht from the 18th Dynasty [62].

Fig.14 View in Sennefer's tomb from the 18th Dynasty [59].

Fig.15 Scene in Rekhmire's tomb from the 18th Dynasty [60].

Fig.16 Scene in Menna's tomb from the 18th Dynasty [61].

Fig.17 Scene in Nakht's tomb from the 18th Dynasty [62].

This project is considered one of the important national projects that raise the name of Egypt high after it was defiled by the hands of the Persian colonialists by destroying some statues of the victorious pharaoh Ramses II, during their rule over Egypt during the 27th and 31st dynasties. Unfortunately, the broken statues remained in place without restoration, and most of them are lying on the ground for thousands of years, the descendants did not move to remove the dust from their profane history and install statues of their victorious leader, Ramses II, in the places where they were. For the sake of these noble meanings, this project came as follows:

- 1- Teams of graduates of the faculties of archaeology in Egypt or abroad who have experience in restoring antiquities (especially rocky ones) and faculty members will be formed.
- 2- Each team takes over one of the statues as follows:
 - Statue of Ramses II falling to the ground in Ramesseum.
 - The fallen statue of Ramses II on the ground in Wadi Al-Sebua (next to Lake Nasser).
 - Statue of Ramses II falling to the ground in Tanis.

- Statue of Ramses II falling to the ground in Memphis.
 - Statue of Ramses II, fallen to the ground in Mit-Rahina (near Memphis).
 - Statue of Ramses II falling to the ground in Memphis.
 - The statue of Ramses II, the upper half of which was shattered, in Abu Simbel temple (part of the head and crown lying on the ground in front of the statue).
 - Statue of Ramses II standing in Thebes's desert (Luxor) {its lower half}.
 - Statues of Ramses II standing in front of the Ramesseum Temple (with their heads broken).
 - The broken statues at Karnak Temple in Luxor.
- 3- Each team prepares a feasibility study on restoring each of the statues and placing them in their original place in the days of families 19 and 20 (some of the research papers presented in the introduction of this paper provide a good start for this effort).
 - 4- The studies shall be submitted to the Ministry of Antiquities to obtain a permit for work and funding, if possible.
 - 5- Because it is an innovative national work, it can be submitted to the Academy of Scientific Research as projects funded by the Academy.
 - 6- It is possible to communicate directly with the President of the Republic to give impetus to these projects and provide the necessary financial support.
 - 7- It is possible to apply to the Egyptian National Academy for Research and to the UNESCO to support this project financially.
 - 8- Some of the statues suggested for this project are presented in Figs.18-25.

- Fig.18: Statue of Pharaoh Ramses II at Ramesseum [63].

Fig.18 Fallen statue of Ramses II at Ramesseum [63].

- Fig.19: Broken feet of Pharaoh Ramses II's statue at Ramesseum [64].

Fig.19 Broken feet of Ramses II at Ramesseum [64].

- Fig.20: Broken statue of Pharaoh Ramses II's statue at Wadi Sebua [65].

Fig.20 Fallen statue of Ramses II at Wadi Sebua [65].

- Fig.21: Broken statue of Pharaoh Ramses II's statue at Tanis [66].

Fig.21 Fallen statue of Ramses II at Tanis [66].

- Fig.22: Broken statue of Pharaoh Ramses II's statue at Mit Rahina [67].

Fig.22 Fallen statue of Ramses II at Mit Rahina [67].

- Fig.23: Broken statue of Pharaoh Ramses II's statue at Abu Simbel [68].

Fig.23 Broken statue of Ramses II at Abu Simbel [68].

- Fig.24: Fallen statue of Pharaoh Ramses III at Memphis [69].

Fig.24 Broken and fallen statue of Ramses II at Memphis [69].

- Fig.25: Broken statues of Pharaoh Ramses II at the Ramesseum temple [70].

different ancient Egyptians locations with complete or partial damage of the Pharaoh's statues.

Fig.25 Statues of Ramses II at the Ramesseum temple [70].

VII. CONCLUSIONS

- The paper presented some archaeological projects from the ancient Egyptian civilization for application nationally or internationally by qualified archaeological graduates and experts.
- The first project presented the idea of exhibitions for some products belonging to some mechanical industries practiced in ancient Egypt. The idea was clarified through application steps and examples from the jewelry, pottery, stone vessels, glass, ladies headdress, basketry and diadem industries.
- The second project presented the idea of producing replicas for specific products. The idea was clarified through application steps and eight examples from different ancient Egyptians industries.
- The third project presented the idea of producing replicas for some of the ancient Egyptian tombs for Kings, Queens and Nobles. The idea was clarified through application steps and two examples from the 18th Dynasty (scene) and 20th Dynasty (relief).
- The fourth project presented the idea of the restoration of some specific tombs of the ancient Egyptians. The idea was clarified through application steps and five examples from the tombs of Nobles that in urgent need to restoration.
- The fifth project presented the idea of the restoration of some of the partially damaged stone statues of Pharaoh Ramses II from the 19th Dynasty. The idea was clarified through application steps and eight examples from

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